

Supplemental Figure 1: Study flow diagram

Supplemental Figure 2: Summary risk of bias as a percentage of all included studies for the effects of SQ-LNS on growth outcomes

Supplemental Figure 3: Forest plot of effect of SQ-LNS on prevalence of severe acute malnutrition (SAM)

LNS, lipid-based nutrient supplements; PR, prevalence ratio.

Individual study estimates were generated from log-binomial regression controlling for baseline measure when available and with clustered observations using robust standard errors for cluster-randomized trials. Pooled estimates were generated using inverse-variance weighting with both fixed and random effects.

Supplemental Figure 4: Forest plot of effect of SQ-LNS on prevalence of very low MUAC

LNS, lipid-based nutrient supplements; MUAC, mid-upper arm circumference; PR, prevalence ratio.

Individual study estimates were generated from log-binomial regression controlling for baseline measure when available and with clustered observations using robust standard errors for cluster-randomized trials. Pooled estimates were generated using inverse-variance weighting with both fixed and random effects.

Supplemental Figure 5: Sensitivity analyses of main effects of SQ-LNS on prevalence ratios for severe acute malnutrition (SAM)

All-trial analysis includes all trials;

Child-LNS-only excludes trial arms that provided both maternal and child LNS;

Multi-component analysis separates comparisons within trials that included multi-component interventions, so that the SQ-LNS vs. no SQ-LNS comparisons were conducted separately between pairs of arms that included the same non-nutrition components (e.g. SQ-LNS+WASH vs. WASH; SQ-LNS vs. Control);

Passive arms excluded analysis excludes passive control arms;

Milk-peanut LNS only analysis excludes arms with SQ-LNS formulations that were not milk and peanut based;

“Zero events trials included” uses estimates generated for certain trials in which 0.5 is substituted for the 0 value in analysis for severe wasting.

LNS, lipid-based nutrient supplements.

Supplemental Figure 6: Sensitivity analyses of main effects of SQ-LNS on prevalence ratios for very low MUAC

All-trial analysis includes all trials;

Child-LNS-only excludes trial arms that provided both maternal and child LNS;

Multi-component analysis separates comparisons within trials that included multi-component interventions, so that the SQ-LNS vs. no SQ-LNS comparisons were conducted separately between pairs of arms that included the same non-nutrition components (e.g. SQ-LNS+WASH vs. WASH; SQ-LNS vs. Control);

Passive arms excluded analysis excludes passive control arms;

Milk-peanut LNS only analysis excludes arms with SQ-LNS formulations that were not milk and peanut based;

“Zero events trials included” uses estimates generated for certain trials in which 0.5 is substituted for the 0 value in analysis for severe wasting.

LNS, lipid-based nutrient supplements; MUAC, mid-upper arm circumference.

Supplemental Figure 7: Forest plot of effect of SQ-LNS on severe wasting prevalence using the rare events sensitivity analysis, with estimates generated for certain trials in which 0.5 is substituted for the 0 value in analysis

LNS, lipid-based nutrient supplements; PR, prevalence ratio.

Individual study estimates were generated from log-binomial regression controlling for baseline measure when available and with clustered observations using robust standard errors for cluster-randomized trials. Pooled estimates were generated using inverse-variance weighting with both fixed and random effects.

Supplemental Figure 8: Forest plot of effect of SQ-LNS on prevalence of concurrent severe stunting and severe wasting

LNS, lipid-based nutrient supplements; PR, prevalence ratio.

Individual study estimates were generated from log-binomial regression controlling for baseline measure when available and with clustered observations using robust standard errors for cluster-randomized trials. Pooled estimates were generated using inverse-variance weighting with both fixed and random effects.

Supplemental figure 9: Forest plots for effects of SQ-LNS on severe wasting stratified by study-level effect modifiers

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These figures are forest plots showing the study-level effect modification of intervention effects. Each figure shows the study-level estimates along with the corresponding pooled estimate grouped by study-level effect modifier category. Individual study estimates were generated from log-binomial regression; controlling for baseline measure when available and with clustered observations using robust standard errors for cluster-randomized trials. Pooled sub-group estimates were generated using inverse-variance weighting random effects. P-value for the difference was estimated using random effects meta-regression with the indicated effect modifier as the predictor of intervention effect size; stratified pooled estimates are presented for each strata.

The labels on the left y-axis correspond to trial level information. The values on the right indicate the study level effect estimate, confidence interval, and weighting for deriving the pooled estimates.

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9A: Stratified by Geographic region

Geographic region

(p -diff = 0.276)

Geographic region – SEAR

Geographic region – AFR

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favours Control

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9B: Stratified by Stunting burden

Stunting burden
(p-diff = 0.343)

Stunting burden – Less than 35%

Stunting burden – More than 35%

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9C: Stratified by Wasting burden

Wasting burden
(p-diff = 0.354)

Wasting burden – Wasting < 10%

Wasting burden – Wasting >= 10%

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9D: Stratified by Malaria prevalence

Malaria prevalence

(p-diff = 0.294)

Malaria prevalence – Less than 10%

Malaria prevalence – At least 10%

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favors Control

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9E: Stratified by Source water quality

Source water quality
(p-diff = 0.035)

Source water quality – Improved

Source water quality – Unimproved

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9F: Stratified by Sanitation

Sanitation
(p-diff = 0.154)

Sanitation – Improved

Sanitation – Unimproved

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9G: Stratified by Supplement duration

Supplement duration

(p-diff = 0.375)

Supplement duration – 12m or less

Supplement duration – > 12m

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9H: Stratified by Frequency of contact

Frequency of contact
(p-diff = 0.710)

Frequency of contact – Monthly

Frequency of contact – Weekly

Supplemental figure 9: Severe wasting prevalence ratio

9I: Stratified by Average SQ-LNS compliance

Average SQ-LNS compliance
(p-diff = 0.549)

Average SQ-LNS compliance – Low

Average SQ-LNS compliance – High

Supplemental figure 10: Forest plots for effects of SQ-LNS on severe stunting stratified by study-level effect modifiers

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These figures are forest plots showing the study-level effect modification of intervention effects. Each figure shows the study-level estimates along with the corresponding pooled estimate grouped by study-level effect modifier category. Individual study estimates were generated from log-binomial regression; controlling for baseline measure when available and with clustered observations using robust standard errors for cluster-randomized trials. Pooled sub-group estimates were generated using inverse-variance weighting random effects. P-value for the difference was estimated using random effects meta-regression with the indicated effect modifier as the predictor of intervention effect size; stratified pooled estimates are presented for each strata.

The labels on the left y-axis correspond to trial level information. The values on the right indicate the study level effect estimate, confidence interval, and weighting for deriving the pooled estimates.

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10A: Stratified by Geographic region

Geographic region

(p -diff = 0.970)

Geographic region – SEAR

Country	Trial	N	N	PR (95% CI)	W
Bangladesh	JiVitA-4 (42)	2838	1244	0.95 (0.78, 1.17)	0.37
Bangladesh	RDNS (43)	1663	815	0.89 (0.67, 1.20)	0.27
Bangladesh	WASH-B (44)	1158	3431	0.71 (0.58, 0.87)	0.37
$I^2 = 0.52, \text{Tau}^2 = 0.01$		5659	5490	0.84 (0.70, 1.01)	

Geographic region – AFR

Burkina Faso	iLiNS-Zinc (45)	1952	664	0.48 (0.38, 0.60)	0.13
Burkina Faso	PROMIS (46)	863	914	0.96 (0.63, 1.47)	0.06
Burkina Faso	PROMIS CS (46)	430	439	0.88 (0.42, 1.82)	0.03
Ghana	GHANA (47)	98	96	0.98 (0.06, 15.43)	0.00
Ghana	iLiNS-DYAD-G (48)	347	692	1.71 (0.58, 5.05)	0.01
Kenya	WASH-B (50)	1457	5137	0.82 (0.67, 1.01)	0.14
Madagascar	MAHAY (51)	1702	1682	1.01 (0.85, 1.21)	0.15
Malawi	iLiNS-DYAD-M (52)	220	444	0.90 (0.55, 1.47)	0.05
Malawi	iLiNS-DOSE (53)	696	241	0.97 (0.70, 1.35)	0.09
Mali	PROMIS (54)	506	506	0.97 (0.64, 1.47)	0.07
Mali	PROMIS CS (54)	952	969	0.73 (0.51, 1.06)	0.08
Zimbabwe	SHINE (HIV-) (55)	1880	1794	0.82 (0.65, 1.04)	0.13
Zimbabwe	SHINE (HIV+) (56)	337	330	0.89 (0.60, 1.30)	0.07
$I^2 = 0.61, \text{Tau}^2 = 0.03$		11440	13908	0.83 (0.73, 0.96)	

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favours Control

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10B: Stratified by Stunting burden

Stunting burden
(p-diff = 0.309)

Stunting burden – Less than 35%

Stunting burden – More than 35%

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favors Control

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10C: Stratified by Wasting burden

Wasting burden
(p-diff = 0.123)

Wasting burden – Wasting < 10%

Wasting burden – Wasting >= 10%

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10D: Stratified by Malaria prevalence

Malaria prevalence
(p-diff = 0.407)

Malaria prevalence – Less than 10%

Country	Trial	N	N	PR (95% CI)	W
Bangladesh	JiVitA-4 (42)	2838	1244	0.95 (0.78, 1.17)	0.15
Bangladesh	RDNS (43)	1663	815	0.89 (0.67, 1.20)	0.12
Bangladesh	WASH-B (44)	1158	3431	0.71 (0.58, 0.87)	0.16
Haiti	HAITI (49)	149	149	1.79 (0.73, 4.42)	0.02
Kenya	WASH-B (50)	1457	5137	0.82 (0.67, 1.01)	0.15
Madagascar	MAHAY (51)	1702	1682	1.01 (0.85, 1.21)	0.17
Zimbabwe	SHINE (HIV-) (55)	1880	1794	0.82 (0.65, 1.04)	0.14
Zimbabwe	SHINE (HIV+) (56)	337	330	0.89 (0.60, 1.30)	0.09
I² = 0.33, Tau² = 0.01		11184	14582	0.88 (0.79, 0.98)	

Malaria prevalence – At least 10%

Burkina Faso	iLiNS-Zinc (45)	1952	664	0.48 (0.38, 0.60)	0.24
Burkina Faso	PROMIS (46)	863	914	0.96 (0.63, 1.47)	0.13
Burkina Faso	PROMIS CS (46)	430	439	0.88 (0.42, 1.82)	0.05
Ghana	GHANA (47)	98	96	0.98 (0.06, 15.43)	0.00
Ghana	iLiNS-DYAD-G (48)	347	692	1.71 (0.58, 5.05)	0.03
Malawi	iLiNS-DYAD-M (52)	220	444	0.90 (0.55, 1.47)	0.10
Malawi	iLiNS-DOSE (53)	696	241	0.97 (0.70, 1.35)	0.17
Mali	PROMIS (54)	506	506	0.97 (0.64, 1.47)	0.13
Mali	PROMIS CS (54)	952	969	0.73 (0.51, 1.06)	0.15
I² = 0.64, Tau² = 0.04		6064	4965	0.81 (0.65, 0.99)	

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10E: Stratified by Source water quality

Source water quality
(p-diff = 0.369)

Source water quality – Improved

Source water quality – Unimproved

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favors Control

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10F: Stratified by Sanitation

Sanitation
(p-diff = 0.533)

Sanitation – Improved

Sanitation – Unimproved

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favors Control

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10G: Stratified by Supplement duration

Supplement duration

(p-diff = 0.572)

Supplement duration – 12m or less

Supplement duration – > 12m

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10H: Stratified by Frequency of contact

Frequency of contact
(p-diff = 0.220)

Frequency of contact – Monthly

Frequency of contact – Weekly

0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 4.0
Ratio
Favors LNS Favors Control

Supplemental figure 10: Severe stunting prevalence ratio

10I: Stratified by Average SQ-LNS compliance

Average SQ-LNS compliance

(p-diff = 0.251)

Average SQ-LNS compliance – Low

Average SQ-LNS compliance – High

